

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

BIBLIOGRAPHICAL MEANS DEDICATED TO NARIMANA NARIMANOVA AS AN INFORMATION RESOURCE FOR PROFESSIONALS IN THE FIELD

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Abstract

Nariman Najaf oglu Narimanov is a public and political figure, writer, publicist, doctor, the first People's Commissar for Foreign Affairs of Azerbaijan. The first Constitution of Azerbaijan is associated with the name of Nariman Narimanov. By the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated May 7, 2019, No. 211, Nariman Narimanov was included in the list of authors whose works were declared state property in the Republic of Azerbaijan. In 1894, N. Narimanov opened the first reading room in Baku. N. Narimanov is the founder of the Azerbaijani national novel - "Bahadur and Sona" and the first historical tragedy ("Nadir Shah"). During his life, N. Narimanov maintained friendly relations with all neighboring republics. A striking example of this is his enormous support for the Turkish War of Independence. When Ataturk offered to repay him for his help, N. Narimanov sent him the following response: "Pashas, there is a tradition in the Turkish people: a brother does not lend money to a brother, a brother holds his brother's hand in any case." The article talks about the role of information resources in a deeper study and promotion of the legacy of Nariman Narimanov, his place in the history of the Azerbaijani people, the history and culture of Azerbaijan in general. It is noted that there are two types of resources dedicated to Nariman Narimanov. The first is primary information resources, and the second is secondary information resources. The study included existing sources of information, emphasizing the important role of specialists in the field of providing information through the analysis of published bibliographic information on literature.

Keywords: Nariman Narimanov, primary information resources, bibliographic resources, research of the heritage of N. Narimanov, information support.

Introduction

In the process of creating personal bibliographic resources, all the works written by the mentioned person, as well as translations and literature about him, are taken as the object of bibliography. The literature coverage of such bibliographic resources is related only to that person. The system of personal bibliographic resources as a whole has a wide bibliographic information potential and plays an important role in the bibliographic search of literature in the field included in this system. One of the main work directions of the National Library named after M.F. Akhundov is the compilation of personal indexes from the series "Prominent personalities of Azerbaijan". One of such fundamental personal bibliographic indicators is the fundamental bibliographic monograph dedicated to Nariman Narimanov, an outstanding state and political figure of Azerbaijan.

As it is known, important works have been done for the celebration of the jubilee of Nariman Narimanov, a prominent state and political figure of Azerbaijan.

On February 14, 2020, President Ilham Aliyev signed a decree on the celebration of the 150th anniversary of Nariman Narimanov. The decree states:

"April 2020 marks the 150th anniversary of the birth of Nariman Najaf oglu Narimanov, a prominent writer and statesman of Azerbaijan [1].

Problem setting

As a famous writer, playwright, publicist and educator, Nariman Narimanov played a major role in enriching Azerbaijani literature with advanced ideas and democratic ideas. His works, which touch on the important issues of the time and whose main goal is a call to enlightenment and cultural advancement, are dominated by a deep humanitarian spirit. Nariman Narimanov's dramaturgy made valuable contributions to the development of Azerbaijani theater. He is a patriotic writer who has a unique and worthy place in the history of national artistic prose, and is also known as the author of serious and relevant journalistic examples.

There is an organic connection between Nariman Narimanov's artistic creativity and his social and political activities. An important part of his life was spent in successive struggles for the people's cause, which he believed in and which he considered the main task of his life and turned it into a sacred act. Despite the extremely complicated conditions aggravated by political clashes, Nariman Narimanov, as a leader who always prioritizes national interests, defended the interests of our people to the utmost extent in relation to the fateful problems. He paid special attention to the preservation of the cultural resources of our past, the purity of the mother tongue, worked with all his might for the development of science, education and culture, and treated with respect and care the personalities who

were the bearers of the national ideology of the time [1].

The socio-political activity of Nariman Narimanov, which left a significant mark in the history of Azerbaijan in the 20th century, was given its due appreciation thanks to the authority and determination of the great leader Heydar Aliyev. National leader Heydar Aliyev initiated the solemn celebration of Nariman Narimanov's 100th and 125th anniversaries, the construction of his magnificent monument in Baku and the creation of his house-museum, as well as the perpetuation of his memory outside the borders of our country.

Guided by paragraph 32 of Article 109 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, I make a decision to ensure the celebration of the 150th anniversary of the birth of Nariman Narimanov, an outstanding writer, public and political figure of Azerbaijan:

1. The Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Azerbaijan together with the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan, taking into account the proposals of the Writers' Union of Azerbaijan, should prepare and implement a plan of events for the 150th anniversary of the outstanding writer and statesman Nariman Narimanov.

2. The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan should resolve the issues arising from this Order.

Ilham ALIYEV, President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Baku city. February 14, 2020.

Collecting the works written about Nariman Narimanov, one of the most prominent figures in the history of social and political thought of Azerbaijan at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, putting them into a system, grouping them and passing them down from generation to generation is one of the biggest tasks facing the bibliography. The creation of such a fundamental bibliographic monograph is a great contribution to the 150th anniversary of the birth of the outstanding writer, publicist, social and political figure Nariman Narimanov.

It should be noted that in general, researches have been conducted in international journals in various directions [3, 8, 9, 10].

The main part

Nariman Karbalayi Najaf oglu Narimanov was born on April 14, 1870 in Tbilisi in a poor family. He entered the Gori Seminary in 1882, graduated from the Seminary in 1890 and was appointed a teacher at the Kizilhajili village primary school in Borchali district of Tbilisi province. In 1891, he moved to Baku, where he started teaching at A. I. Pobedonostsev's special gymnasium, and at the same time, he was engaged in extensive cultural-educational, literary and political activities. In 1894, Narimanov managed to open the first mass national reading room for the Turkish-Muslim population in Baku. The fund of the reading room he created contained both Eastern and Russian, as well as European literature. Newspapers, magazines and books were sent to the fund of the reading room

through charity from Istanbul, Sofia, Cairo, Tehran, Tabriz and other cities. Nariman Narimanov, who regularly publishes journalistic articles, has also written textbooks for students of Azerbaijani and Russian languages [11].

Nariman Narimanov's first pen experience is the play "Ignorance". The play "Ignorance" was published in the Azerbaijani language in 1894 and was staged in Baku for the first time in 1895. Narimanov spent the income from the performance on the reading room. During this period, Narimanov also wrote the works "Trouble of the Tongue" or "Shamdan Bey" (1895), "Bahadır and Sona" (1896-1908), "Nadir Shah" (1899). He laid the foundation of the first national novel in Azerbaijani literature with his work "Bahadır va Sona", and the first historical tragedy with his work "Nadir Shah". Narimanov, who clearly shows the social and psychological problems of the time in his works, even touched on those points in his historical works. All the negative aspects of absolutism are clearly written in the play "Nadir Shah", which he published in 1899. Narimanov's scientific and journalistic activity served to free the society from inertia and national awakening of the Turkish-Muslim population.

Constantly striving for new knowledge, Narimanov studied humanities by teaching at the Baku real school since 1896, and in 1902 he took an external exam and received the certificate of the Baku Men's Gymnasium named after Alexander III.

In the same year, he entered the medical faculty of Novorossiysk Imperial University in Odessa. During his studies at the university, Narimanov also created a theater troupe consisting of students. Later, he returned to Baku and chaired the founding commission of the 1st congress of Muslim teachers. In 1906, he returned to Odessa to finish his studies. In 1907-1908, the work "Nadir Shah" was staged in the big city theaters of the Volga region, Turkestan, South Caucasus, as well as in Tehran. Returning to Baku in 1908, Narimanov worked in the city hospital, and was engaged in political activities along with his medical activities.

Narimanov, who was assigned to Tiflis in 1909, worked as a doctor and therapist there, but was accused of having connections with Iranian revolutionaries and was arrested. After 6 months in prison, he was exiled to Astrakhan for two years. In addition to continuing his medical activities, he participated in cultural and mass events and did not stop his revolutionary activities. At the same time, Narimanov, who was elected chairman of the Astrakhan People's University, was also a member of the city дума. The question of his activity has spread far and wide. It was even mentioned in the "Paris" newspaper published in France that "Nariman Narimanov's propaganda was a great success among the Muslim population living in the Astrakhan province." Narimanov, who has been working in various positions in Astrakhan, asked, "With what slogan are we going to the Caucasus?" showed his loyalty to the idea of communism with his programmatic article. He believed that this idea would lead to general equality and ultimately to the elimination of all problems and the establishment of a just society [1].

While in exile, Narimanov wrote many articles in "Burkhani-taraqqi", "Astrakhanski listok", "Astrakhanski kray", "Astrakhanski vestnik" and other newspapers, as well as continued his revolutionary and medical activities. On August 21, 1911, after ending his life in exile, he was allowed to return to Baku. Returning to Baku in July 1913, Narimanov also continued his literary activities in those years. Adib wrote the story "The Adventure of a Village" (1915) and the short story "Pir" (1917), published articles in the press, and staged the novel "Bahadır va Sona". Narimanov was also a member of the Baku Muslim Public Organizations Bureau. At that time, "Hummet" newspaper was published under his editorship.

In August 1919, N. Narimanov was called to Moscow and appointed as Deputy People's Commissar for Eastern Affairs in the People's Commissariat of Foreign Affairs (MFA) of the RSFSR [1].

In April 1920, Azerbaijan was occupied by military means, and repressions began here. Although Narimanov was elected in absentia to the governing bodies of the Soviet Republic established in Azerbaijan, he was not allowed to return to Baku. He was able to come to Baku on May 16 only after the end of the first wave of repressions. It was Narimanov who made it possible for many of the members of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic to go abroad and thereby saved them from being subjected to Soviet repression. Because of all this, Narimanov was accused of "nationalism", and his ideas were insultingly called "Narimanovism".

He had exceptional services in establishing friendly relations between Russia and Turkey. Narimanov, who deeply sympathized with the Turkish people's war of independence and Atatürk, was widely covered in the Turkish press. According to the Kars Treaty signed in 1921 with the efforts of Narimanov, the pressure on Nakhchivan was removed and Turkey acted as a guarantor of this. In 1922, Narimanov participated in the international conference held in Genoa as part of the Soviet delegation, and later he was elected chairman of the Union Council of the Transcaucasian Federation.

In 1925, writing of the Great Soviet Encyclopedia was started at the suggestion of Nariman Narimanov. Many firsts, including the preparation of the first constitution of the USSR (1924), are connected with Narimanov's name. Not only was the prominent social and political figure an active initiator and organizer of the convening of the First Congress of Eastern Peoples held in Baku, he also played a major role in convening the First Turkological Congress in Baku. Narimanov was a person with unique original ideas in the history of school and pedagogical ideas of Azerbaijan. Nariman Narimanov paid special attention to the national and cultural progress of the Azerbaijani people, religious problems, the granting of state status to the Azerbaijani language, national intellectuals and education. He came from among the hard-working people, spoke on their behalf and worked for their freedom, public education and progress of culture until the end of his life. N. Narimanov died suddenly in

Moscow on March 19, 1925, and was buried on the Golden Square, near the Kremlin walls.

The memory of the great social and political figure, outstanding dramatist Nariman Narimanov has been immortalized by our country. Thanks to the initiative and determination of the great leader Heydar Aliyev, Narimanov's social and political activity received a deserved appreciation, and the 100th anniversary of his birth was celebrated with a ceremony. On November 6, 1977, a memorial museum was opened in the apartment where the famous writer lived, according to the instructions of the national leader. Also, there are district, metro station, avenues and streets, monuments, schools named after Narimanov in Baku city. Also, a monument to Narimanov was erected in Ulyanovsk, Russia (1977) and Marneuli, Georgia (1983), where Nariman Narimanov once worked. In 1982, a commemorative plaque with his granite bas-relief portrait was hung in the building where he lived in Moscow.

It should be noted that the topic dedicated to information resources on the works of prominent political and state figures of Azerbaijan is a broad topic of the subject "Socio-political information resources" at the Department of Bibliography of Baku State University [8]. The period of Nariman Narimanov is taught separately. Until now, when talking about the publication and bibliography of the writer's works during teaching, no such fundamental bibliographic work has been published except for "Nariman Narimanov (1870-1970): bibliographic index" on the occasion of the 100th anniversary of the birth of the prominent political statesman Nariman Narimanov in 1970. The publication of Nariman Narimanov's works in bulk on the occasion of the anniversary was an important event in the field of studying the legacy of the public figure. In connection with the anniversary, the scientific-assistant bibliography of N. Narimanov's works was published in "Azernashr" in 1972 by bibliographer-scientist Farman Bayramov. This bibliographic index, which includes 1777 sources, occupies a special place in the history of the bibliography of Nariman Narimanov's legacy due to its comprehensiveness. The material published under the name "Bibliographic index of Nariman Narimanov's works" consists of 2 parts. In the first part, there is a bibliographic description of N. Narimanov's works in the Azerbaijani language, and in the second part, his works in the Russian language [5].

The bibliographic index covers the period from 1870 to 1970. During this period, bibliographic information about Narimanov's heritage, that is, his life and activities, biography, publication of his works, social and political activities, etc. sources of various nature are reflected in the bibliographic index. In the bibliographic index, Narimanov's works are systematized and described according to the date of publication. Narimanov's published works as well as a large number of articles published in periodicals are reflected in the bibliographic index. One of the most interesting aspects of the bibliographic index for readers is that the literature about Narimanov is

systematized and described on various topics related to a certain period of his creativity.

"About Nariman Narimanov's artistic creativity", "About Narimanov's pedagogical activity", "About Narimanov's medical art", etc. the systematization of literature is of great importance in the study of Narimanov's works and heritage. In the bibliographic index, the works of N. Narimanov in Russian are also systematized and printed according to the date of publication. The bibliographic index printed in 2 languages is considered an important bibliographic source for studying the life and activities of a great personality. The historical facts and bibliographic information given in the I and II parts of the index are very interesting in answering the reader's requests. When the bibliographic index was published in connection with the jubilee, the main goal was to fully cover all his works and the literature about him, and to fulfill the task set in connection with the compilation of the bibliographic index. Therefore, the bibliographic index, which has rich sources, helps the bibliographic provision of individual readers in relation to the various fields indicated above. The bibliographic index is wider due to the direction of the reader. This is related to the multifaceted nature of N. Narimanov's life and activities.

The newly released bibliographic work is a great success of the National Library of Azerbaijan in this field, and its bibliographic activity is highly commendable. Nariman Narimanov (Nariman Najaf oglu Narimanov): Bibliography was published in 2020. If we look at the grouping of documents that are the object of bibliography in the bibliographic monograph, we will see that they were released in the "Prominent personalities of Azerbaijan" series. The text of the Decree signed by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Mr. Ilham Aliyev on the occasion of the 150th anniversary of the writer is given in Azerbaijani and Russian languages. Providing the text "About the indicator" in two languages at the same time provides information about its structure and is very valuable for Russian-speaking readers. The section "The main dates of the life and activities of Nariman Narimanov" is given in Azerbaijani and Russian languages. In the "Prominent personalities Nariman Narimanov" section, the words of our national leader Heydar Aliyev are given first:

"Nariman Narimanov went through a complicated and difficult path, starting his career as an educator-democrat ... as a political leader and organizer, he served the people with all his talent and all the warmth of his heart. His name... is inextricably linked with the heroic struggle of Azerbaijani workers."

"Nariman Narimanov is still with us today. Here, with its huge stature, it rises above the waves of the old Caspian Sea. The hero, who gained fame in revolutionary battles and creative socialist work, stands tall in Baku and proudly looks at the plains of our republic, which has changed beyond recognition during the years of Soviet rule, and carefully inspects the multinational groups of hard workers who have come to meet the brave fighter who fought for the happiness of the people [2].

**Heydar Aliyev,
nationwide leader**

"There is an organic connection between Nariman Narimanov's artistic creativity and social and political activities. An important part of his life was spent in successive struggles for the people's cause, which he believed in and which he considered the main task of his life and turned it into a sacred act. Despite the extremely complicated conditions aggravated by political clashes, Nariman Narimanov, as a leader who always prioritizes national interests, defended the interests of our people to the utmost extent in relation to the fateful problems...

The socio-political activity of Nariman Narimanov, which left a significant mark in the history of Azerbaijan in the 20th century, was given its due appreciation thanks to the authority and determination of the great leader Heydar Aliyev. National leader Heydar Aliyev initiated the solemn celebration of Nariman Narimanov's 100th and 125th anniversaries, the construction of his magnificent monument in Baku and the creation of his house-museum, as well as the perpetuation of his memory outside the borders of our country."

**Ilham Aliyev,
President of the Republic of Azerbaijan**

"When I accompanied Comrade N. Narimanov on his visit to the Republic, I saw and believed with my own eyes how much authority and influence he had among the working people of Azerbaijan... Comrade Narimanov was welcomed everywhere by the people with a sincere ceremony. Large rallies were organized at meeting places.

In all these rallies and meetings, Narimanov was able to find a language close to and familiar to the people and to solve the issues... This trip was undoubtedly of great importance for the strengthening of the new structure at that time.

**Samad agha Agamali oglu,
publicist, USSR statesman**

"Nariman was very caring towards the child and me. He would tell me to pay more attention to the children."

**Mrs. Kulsum Narimanova
Wife of N. Narimanov**

Novelty

The wise opinions of twenty-six people, including the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev, publicist, statesman Samad agha Agamali oglu, N. Narimanov's wife Gulsum Narimanova, were given. At the end of the section, three poets - People's poet Rasul Rza's poem "Nariman" on the occasion of N. Narimanov's death, Turkish writer, journalist Irfan Ulkun's poem "Narimanov" etc. has found its reflection. One of the interesting sections is dedicated to "Wise words and opinions of Nariman Narimanov". 58 sayings of Nariman Narimanov were included in this section. Examples of wise sayings:

"The one who knows the value of the Motherland is the one who has a spiritual connection with the

Motherland, cries together with the Motherland and laughs together. Therefore, it is necessary to leave this slogan in the East: if everyone works not for himself, but for the Motherland, he has the right to choose and be chosen", and at the end, we can show the poet's poem "Oğlum Najafa".

In the "Works" section, a bibliographic description of his books was given and it was revealed that his first book was "Ignorance" published in 1894. From 1894 to 2020, 64 books were published. In the "Works published in books and periodicals" section, the first literary works appear. That is, during the monitoring of the bibliographic monograph, it was found that 11 titles were published between 1958 and 2014, and in the subsection "Literary-critical and journalistic articles" between 1904 and 2017. The bibliographic description of sources is reflected in 302 names, in the subsection "Reports and speeches" in 116 names between 1906-1972, in the subsection "Decrees, orders and orders

signed by Nariman Narimanov" in 287 names between 1920-1990. ((Diagram 1.)

In the section "About the life and creativity of Nariman Narimanov" books are listed first. It was found out that 89 names between 1925 and 2020, and 1504 names between 1890 and 2020 in the subsection "Articles published in periodicals and collections", let's note that N. Narimnanov 100 years, 120 years and 150 years subsections are also given. 184 sources between the years 1894-2020 in the subsection "About N. Narimanov's artistic creation", 200 names between "Nariman Narimanov in fiction and art" between 1906-2020, and 1968-2020 in the subsection "Perpetuation of the memory of N. Narimanov". 137 titles of literature were included between the years.

In the "Dissertations and auto-abstracts" section, the bibliographic description of 29 works between 1960 and 2018 are necessary sources for field specialists.

(Diagram 2.)

Diagram 1.

The diagram was designed by the author (1).

Diagram 2.

The diagram was designed by the author (2).

Sections and subsections are of great importance for following the literature in Russian. So, let's pay attention to the printing of literature in Russian, first of all, books.

1899-2002 in 23 titles in the "Books" section of his works, 232 titles in the period 1896-2018 in the "Articles, reports and speeches section published in periodicals and collections", 1921 in the "About the life

and activities of N. Narimanov" section - Books in 57 titles between 2020, "Articles published in journals and periodicals" in 621 titles between 1895-2020, "About N. Narimanov's literary and artistic creativity" in 56 titles between 1895-2020, in the subsection "Nariman Narimanov in literature and art" 1899-1987 in 64 years, Nariman The perpetuation of Narimanov's memory was circulated in 35 titles between 1930-2016, and in 39 titles in the "Dissertations and abstracts" section between 1958-2016. (Diagram 3.)

There are works published in "Other foreign languages" in the bibliographic monograph. For example, 14 names in Turkish between 1993-2019, 1

name in Arabic (1984), 11 names in English between 1977-2010, 2 names in Persian between 1922-2020, and 1984-2020 in French. 2 works under the name between 1922-1925 and 2 in 1922-1925 photo, 4 names in German language in 1904-1984, 12 names in Georgian language in 1907-2020, 3 names in Uzbek language in 1981, 4 names in Ukrainian language in 1985-2020, in Tatar language 1908-2013- in 2 names in 1925, in Udmurt language in 1 name, In Armenian language in 1899-1988 in 4 names etc. it is possible to obtain information about the source.

(Diagram 4.)

Diagram 3.

The diagram was designed by the author (3).

Diagram 4.

The diagram was designed by the author (4).

The section "Nariman Narimanov in the world's libraries" is also very noteworthy in terms of the prompt transfer of information in the global information space. Thus, the United States Library of Congress has 7 works and literature about 27, the National Library of Russia has 55 names, the State Library of Russia has 37 names, the National Library of Belarus has 17 names, the National Library of Moldova has 1 name, the Parliamentary National Library of Georgia has 5 names, the Turkish National Library has 2 names, 2

names in the German National Library, 5 names in the British Library, 1 name in the Latvian National Library, Estonian National 5 titles in his library, 1 title in the National Library of Poland, 2 titles in the National Library of Serbia, 5 titles in the National Library of Finland, 1 title in the National Library of Norway, 2 titles in the National Library of Denmark, 1 title in the National Library of Tatarstan. "Nariman Narimanov in world university libraries." in the section, 78 works from different countries such as Germany, New York,

Washington, etc collected in the library. In the "Appendices" section, Appendix 1, in the "Materials preserved in the archival offices of the Republics of Azerbaijan and Georgia" section, the provision of 435 names of archival materials are important sources for researchers of Nariman Narimanov's heritage. Providing information about 25 researchers of Nariman

Narimanov in Appendix 2 is one of the positive aspects of the monograph. As one of the interesting aspects of the bibliographic index, we see that there are 18 artists with works on the subject of Nariman Narimanov given in Appendix 3.

(Diagram 5.)

Diagram 5.

The diagram was designed by the author (5). [1]

Conclusion

Auxiliary indicators are also one of the important elements in bibliography. The fact that the bibliographic resource we are talking about has a rich auxiliary apparatus indicates its information capacity. It is appropriate to provide auxiliary indicators such as "Alphabetical index of his works", "Alphabetical index of his books", "Alphabetical index of his artistic works", "Alphabetical index of his reports and speeches", "Alphabetical index of his articles, feuilletons and letters" and "Alphabetical index of authors writing about Nariman Narimanov". Authors' alphabetical index" is important because it helps to search for authors from a bibliographic source, on the other hand, statistical analysis of each author is performed according to the number of works written about that person, and the ranking of authors is determined. From this point of view, the ranking of prominent scientists in the top ten about N.Narimanov is as follows:

Ahmadov T.- 88
Ibrahimov M. - 35
Ahmadov H.-34
Ahmadova F.-24
Kahramanova R.-22

Hasanzade N.-19
Mammadov M.-19
Gurbanov Sh.-16
Mammadli Q.-15
Mir Jalal-14
In Russian:
Guliyev Q.-23
Ibrahimov M.-10, etc.

When paying attention to the list of authors, it was possible to specify that the first place in the rating was Professor Teymur Ahmadov. Along with these auxiliary indicators, in Russian, there is also an index of names of N. Narimanov published in other languages and an alphabetical index of authors writing in other languages.

In the 688-page bibliographic monograph published in 2020, N.Narimanov's books, works published in periodicals, textbooks, anthologies were reflected, as well as rich material about his life and creativity, social and political activity was collected. In the bibliographic monograph covering the years 1890-2020, the sections "Nariman Narimanov in the world libraries" and "Nariman Narimanov in the world university libraries" were also given for the first time.

The materials of the Memorial Museum of N. Narimanov in Baku were also used.

The bibliographic work is a great success of the National Library named after M.F. Akhundov in this field. We hope that our students, teachers, bibliographers, library workers, and general readers will get more information through the bibliographic monograph.

The scientific editor of the bibliographic index, which meets the standards of modern bibliography, including the methodology of bibliography, is Professor Karim Tahirov, Honored Worker of Culture, the editor is Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor Teymur Ahmadov, the compilers are Madina Valiyeva, Mehriban Jafarova and Halimakhatun Manafova. Such bibliographic resources play an important role in the research of Nariman Narimanov's legacy and in the provision of information to field experts.

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